
THE MAIN CAUSES AND RISK FACTORS OF ONCOLOGICAL DISEASES.

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Introduction: The spread of dangerous oncological diseases and death from them have a great socio-economic importance. Among the causes of death of the population, oncological diseases occupy one of the leading places, and it, in turn, leads to a decrease in the average life expectancy of the population and great economic damage. At the same time, the most essential component of fighting against this diseases is that analyzing them in relation to the environment. In addition, the study of the prevalence of malignant tumor diseases allows to determine the areas that attract the attention of medical personnel, the external environmental factors that cause the spread of malignant tumor diseases, the risk groups of the population, and to develop measures aimed at their recovery. It is important for the social, ecological and economic stability of the region.

Purpose: One of the main reasons for the increase in disability from dangerous oncological diseases is that they are diagnosed later stages in outpatient clinics. First of all, this is due to the inattention of the population to their own health, the fact that medical experts neglect the importance of oncological diseases, pre-tumor chronic diseases, and the ineffectiveness of preventive examinations, dispensary monitoring and control conducted among the population. For this reason, it is necessary to organize and carry out on time measures for the prevention of oncological diseases among the population and the improvement of the medical level of the population.

Materials and methods: Statistical analysis of prevention and incidence of oncological diseases.

In the last century, the number of countries in the world increased almost four times, and today their number exceeds 200. As a result, it led to a change not only in the demographic trend, but also in the oncological situation. By 2050, the number of people over the age of 60 is expected to be higher than the number of children under the age of 15 in the world and all its continents. This leads to the well-known "demographic shift" in many developing countries, which naturally occurs as a result of declining death rates and a somewhat slower decline in birth rates. By the

middle of the 21st century, a majority of the population over 75 years of age is expected to suffer from and die from some form of chronic non-infectious disease, including cancer. About two thousand large and medium-sized enterprises operate in the Republic of Uzbekistan, they have more than 70 thousand fixed harmful sources, which emit more than 150 harmful substances into the atmosphere, more than 50 of them are of great importance. Geographical location of the Republic of Uzbekistan, especially economic activity, with the prevalence of two main external factors that lead to the growth of oncological diseases among the population: high solar radiation and chemical carcinogens. In many Associations of Independent States, lung cancer is the leading cause of cancer in men, followed by stomach cancer and breast cancer in women. Disability from dangerous tumor diseases takes the second place after cardiovascular diseases.

Currently, despite the high efficiency of treatment of patients with stage I and II cancer, the percentage of patients with early primary detection remains low. Every fourth patient is diagnosed with cancer after metastasis.

Among the causes of death of the population, tumor diseases take the second place after cardiovascular diseases. According to the World Health Organization, oncological diseases account for 13% of the causes of death of the population in the world, this figure is equal to 16% in the Russian Federation.

There is no single cause of oncological diseases. In fact, there are several of them. Every day, thousands of people in the world find out that they are suffering from new extremely dangerous oncological diseases. It is difficult to say in one word that this or that is the reason for the occurrence of any oncological diseases. But nevertheless, the etiology of dangerous tumor:

1. Unhealthy and irregular diet;
2. Obesity, sedentary lifestyle;
3. Smoking, drugs, excessive alcohol consumption;
4. External factors - the effect of radiation, industrial waste;
5. Genetic tendency;
6. Viruses;
7. Depression;
8. weakened immune system.

The risk factors leading to the development of oncological diseases can be listed as follows: hereditary factors, endocrine disorders, smoking, ultraviolet and other radiations, chemical carcinogens, dietary habits, environmental factors and etc.

The prevalence and "rejuvenation" of oncological diseases can be said to be a social problem at the state level. Currently, there are many different hypotheses about the occurrence of cancer, and in some cases, people themselves are the cause of their origin.

The main causes of oncological diseases:

Food Carcinogens: Ultimately, the human body produces what it eats. According to statistics, 1/3 of the causes of oncological diseases are related to improper nutrition. That's why scientists consider the origin of oncological diseases to be the result of the effect of carcinogens that enter the human body with food. When eaten irrationally, substances in many habitual foods can cause disease. First of all, they include simple carbohydrates, trans fats. That is why it is necessary to consume more plant products - vegetables and fruits. But herbal products are not always safe, because they may contain nitrite, nitrate, which is considered a carcinogen, and benzopyrene, which is produced by smoking. Therefore, it is recommended to exclude products containing these harmful substances from the diet.

Genetic tendency. One of the second causes of oncological diseases is genetic predisposition. People who do not belong to each risk group have a 20% chance of developing oncological diseases. And in the risk group, this probability is reliably high.

Viruses. In the history of oncological diseases, it has been determined that viruses can cause the spread of oncological diseases. Papilloma virus has been proven in many scientific studies to cause cervical cancer in women. A rare aggressive form of leukemia has been found to develop in people infected with the T-lymphotropic virus; primary liver cancer can be explained by infection with V and C virus, which causes various chronic hepatitis. So, according to statistics, viruses cause every 10th cancer.

Unhealthy habits - alcohol consumption and smoking. Many studies have found a fairly reliable link between smoking and cancer. This applies primarily to lung cancer. Smokers are more likely to develop cancer of the esophagus, larynx, oral cavity and other organs. About 1 in 5 cancer deaths are directly attributable to smoking. Excessive consumption of alcohol has also been found to cause cancer.

Negative influence of the external environment. Many carcinogens in the environment can cause cancer. Examples of oncogenic factors are many chemicals and the effects of radiation on the body. They include many household chemicals: asbestos, some plastics. Car smoke also contains many carcinogenic substances.

Industrial emissions: benzene, formaldehyde, dioxins can be added to the list of carcinogenic substances.

Depression. Currently, many scientists believe that prolonged depression and stress can lead to the development of oncological diseases. Although stress does not directly cause tumor diseases, strong and long-lasting stresses can weaken the body's immune status and sharply reduce the protection against cancers.

Lack of physical activity due to diet, overweight and obesity. Proper nutrition is one of the most important approaches in the fight against cancer. Overweight, obesity can be cause many cancers: esophageal, rectal, breast, endometrial, and kidney cancers.

Occupation-induced carcinogens and radiation. At present, more than 40 carcinogenic substances associated with professional activity have been identified. At the same time, it is recommended to exclude from the diet products that contain these harmful radioactive substances .

Prevention of oncological diseases

Prevention is the most effective strategic "weapon" in the fight against oncological diseases. In modern medicine, 3 types of active prevention of cancer are distinguished: primary, secondary, tertiary prevention.

Primary prevention - primary prevention includes measures such as a healthy lifestyle and proper organization of a rational, healthy diet, raising the body's immunity, quitting smoking, not consuming too much alcohol, physical activity, maintaining a normal body weight, and preventing the effects of carcinogenic substances implementation is included.

Secondary prevention includes the fight against precancerous diseases, implementation of preventive measures and early detection of cancer, effective treatment in time.

Tertiary prevention - prevention of relapses and recurrence of oncological disease.

Conclusion: Prevention is the most effective method in the fight against oncological diseases. In modern medicine, 3 types of active cancer prevention are distinguished: primary, secondary, and tertiary prevention. Currently, many scientists believe that prolonged depression and stress can lead to the development of oncological diseases. Although stress does not directly cause tumor diseases, strong and long-lasting stresses can weaken the body's immune status and sharply reduce the protection against tumors.

Lack of physical activity due to diet, overweight and obesity. Proper nutrition is one of the most important approaches in the fight against cancer. Currently, more

than 40 carcinogenic substances have been identified in relation to occupational activity. It is necessary to carry out in-depth medical examinations of the population in a timely manner, to take the detected diseases under the control of the dispensary in a timely manner, and to apply adequate treatment measures.

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